

THE EFFECT OF SYMMETRIC AND ASYMMETRIC VARIOUS BOUNDARY CONDITIONS IN PARALLEL PLATES

¹Moses, Felix Oghenerobor, ²Osho, Femi Timothy, ³Akinbobola Akinyemi Olufunminiyi

^{1,2} Department of Mathematics, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria.

³ Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State, Nigeria.

¹felixoghene9@gmail.com, ²oshoft@aceondo.edu.ng, ³akinbobola2006@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT This paper considers a combination of symmetric and asymmetric boundary conditions on thermal explosion with Arrhenius kinetics for a slab (parallel plates); the formulated energy equation was non-dimensionalized. Some realistic assumptions will convert the energy conservation equation into dimensionless form, and the resulting nonlinear ordinary differential equation under various boundary conditions will be analytically solved using Frank-Kamenetskii's methods. Variable separation and integration embedded in MAPLE 17 Platform. The graphical display of the effect of the emerging parameters (Dimensionless surface temperature, critical maximum and critical Frank-Kamenetskii numbers are presented. The result shows that the maximum critical temperature increases with increasing dimensionless temperature and decreasing critical Fran-Kamenetskii number for asymmetric model. The symmetric model was found to serve as limiting case to the asymmetric. The study concluded that changing the boundary conditions model was of the parallel Plates significantly alters the critical maximum temperature and the critical Frank-Kamenetskii number. The results were compared with previous studies in literature.

KEYWORDS: Arrhenius Kinetics, Thermal Explosion, Frank-Kamenetskii number, Symmetric Boundary Condition, Asymmetric Boundary Condition.

I. INTRODUCTION

It was demonstrated that the original formulation of the problem by Semenov (1928) correctly characterizes the phenomena and explains the cause of the explosion after a review and analysis of the historical evolution of the thermal-explosion theory. Semenov demonstrated that an explosion happens when a solid's internal heat creation surpasses its external heat dissipation. According to Frank-Kamenetskii's (1969) critique of Semenov's reasoning, the explosion was caused by a temperature differential between the solid's surface and center. His well-known and clever small-temperature model and the resulting differential equation solution warped the problem and slowed down the process of fully comprehending it. Frank-Kamenetskii came to the conclusion that an explosion happens when there is no way to solve the issue. The validity of Semenov's formulation was confirmed by Donaldson and Tsao's (2006) precise solution to the problem. The problem's physics was fully understood after more research on how reactant use affected the issue. A violent response between the overcharged anode and the high electrolyte temperatures that causes an exothermic reaction between the delithiated cathode and electrolyte could be the cause of thermal explosion (Ohsaki et al., 2005). When a chemical system goes through an exothermic reaction, insufficient heat is extracted from the system, causing the reaction process to become self-heating. This results in a thermal explosion. But according to thermal explosion theory, the rate at which heat is generated by the reaction

increases with successive heating until it surpasses the rate at which heat is lost from the region. The computation of heat gain and loss can be used to determine the particular ignition temperature at which an explosion will occur at a given mixture composition and pressure. Either an increase in temperature or the lengthening of the reaction chain accelerates the reaction, causing the transition from combustion to explosion. Thermal explosion is the first, and chain explosion is the second.

If the heat released by the exothermic chemical reaction exceeds the rate at which heat is lost from the body to its surroundings, then an unstable build-up of heat inside a body can occur. This is because the increase in the internal temperature causes the reaction rate to increase, so more heat is generated, leading to a further increase in temperature. If the increase in the reaction rate outweighs the increase in the rate at which heat is lost to the surroundings, an unstable thermal runaway /explosion can occur (Brain, 2019).

The purpose of this study with Arrhenius kinetics has attracted a great deal of interest from researchers across the globe in the past few decades because of its occurrence, as seen in volcanic eruption, nuclear plants etc. However, little is known about the combined mixture of symmetric and asymmetric boundary conditions on thermal explosion with Arrhenius kinetics for a slab; hence, this paper. The statement of the problem of thermal explosion with Arrhenius kinetics has attracted a great deal of interest from researchers in the past few decades because of its occurrence, as seen in volcanic eruption, nuclear plants etc. However, relatively little is known about the combined mixture of symmetric and asymmetric boundary conditions on thermal explosion with Arrhenius kinetics for a slab; hence, this study. However, some of the objectives of this study is/are to: formulate an energy balance equation for the thermal explosion in parallel plates with Arrhenius kinetics, solve the formulated energy equation using standard techniques and examine how different boundary conditions affect the thermal explosion with Arrhenius kinetics. The study of thermal explosion with Arrhenius kinetics has attracted a great deal of interest from researchers in the past few decades because of its occurrence, as seen in volcanic eruption and nuclear plants. However, relatively little is known about the combined mixture of symmetric and asymmetric conditions on thermal explosion with Arrhenius kinetics for a slab; hence, this study.

A. CONCEPTUALIZATION/DEFINITION OF TERMS

For a better understanding of later discussions, the following definitions of important terms used in this study are given below:

Definition 1.1: (Combustion)

When fuel and oxygen react chemically, heat and light energy are released. This process is called Combustion.

General Equation: $Fuel + O_{2(g)} \rightarrow Waste + Energy$

Definition 1.2: (Chemical Kinetics)

The study of chemical reaction rates is known as chemical kinetics.

Definition 1.3: (Steady state) A system is said to be steady when variables (such as velocity, temperature, density etc.) Constant with time (that is $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} = 0$) (Schlichting&Gersten, 2017).

Definition 1.4: (Arrhenius Equation)

An Arrhenius Equation shows how a chemical reaction's rate constant depends on its absolute temperature, a pre-exponential factor, and other reaction constants.

Definition 1.5: (Boundary Conditions)

Boundary conditions: these constraints, which are independent of time, specify the value that a solution must take in a geographical area.

Definition 1.6: (Thermal Explosion)

Thermal Explosion: An explosion is a sudden, severe rise in volume and energy release, typically accompanied by the production of high temperatures and the emission of gasses. It's an event that once initiated grows rapidly and initially unbounded.

Definition 1.8: (Self-Heating)

A process known as "self-heating" occurs when a material heats up by releasing heat from ongoing chemical reactions without absorbing heat from its environment.

Definition 1.9: (Criticality)

When $f(x)$ is a function of a single real variable, the critical point is a value in the domain of f where its derivative is 0 (i.e. $f'(x) = 0$).

Definition 2.0: (Heat Generation)

This is the conversion of one form of energy (such as nuclear, electrical, chemical energy) into heat energy in a medium. A lot of heat transfer applications involve heat generation and this heat generation according to (Azim and Chowdhury, 2013) modifies the temperature distribution. Heat transfer by natural convection significantly influences temperatures of power generating systems (Theodore et al., 2011).

II. METHODOLOGY

The study presents the fundamental energy equation for the Arrhenius-kinetic thermal explosion in parallel plates under varied circumstances of the boundaries. First, the fundamental equation of energy is presented, followed by a discussion of the model assumptions that were used to create the governing equations. The dimensionless Heat transport properties are covered and variables utilized in non-dimensionalizing the constructed equation are defined. A demonstration and discussion of the integration technique used to solve the given problem are provided.

A. Equation of Conservation of Energy

According to the principle of energy conservation, the quantity of work performed on a system and the amount of heat it receives cause the system's internal energy to rise proportionately. The energy equation controls heat transport in a medium when chemical reactions and insignificant radiant energy are present:

$$\rho C_p \frac{DT}{Dt} = K \nabla^2 T + \phi + e_g \tag{1.1}$$

Where C_p the specific heat at constant pressure, T is the temperature, ϕ is the viscous dissipation function, k is the thermal conductivity, e_g is the heat generation term.

B. Problem Formulation

A stationary one-dimensional parallel plate of a reacting material having thickness $2L$ with its plane surfaces maintained at different boundary conditions is being considered. Figures 1 and 2 show the geometry and co-ordinates system of our problem.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The energy equation in (1.1) above was reduced with some assumptions to give:

$$k \frac{d^2T}{dx^2} + A\Delta R\rho \exp(-E/RT) = 0 \tag{1.2}$$

An equation (1.2) is the energy equation subject to some assumptions used. The temperature T and distance y are rescaled so as to compare terms in the equations without reference to units. The temperature equations are non-dimensionalized with the variables:

$$\begin{cases} z = \frac{x}{l} \\ \theta = \frac{E}{RT_A}(T - T_A) = \frac{1}{\beta T_A}(T - T_A) \end{cases} \tag{1.3}$$

The equation (1.2) is reduced to give a dimensionless temperature equation:

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dz^2} = -A\Delta H_{R\rho} \left(\frac{r^2}{k}\right) \left(\frac{E}{RT_A^2}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT_A}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\theta}{1+\beta\theta}\right) \tag{1.4}$$

Where:

$$\delta = A\Delta H_{R\rho} \left(\frac{r^2}{k}\right) \left(\frac{E}{RT_A^2}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT_A}\right) \exp\left(\frac{\theta}{1+\beta\theta}\right) \tag{1.5}$$

is the Frank-Kamenetskii number.

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dz^2} = -\delta \exp\left(\frac{\theta}{1+\beta\theta}\right) \tag{1.6}$$

When $\beta \rightarrow 0$, equation (1.6) becomes:

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dz^2} = -\delta \exp(\theta) \tag{1.7}$$

To obtain the solution of the linear ordinary differential Equation (1.8), we multiply both sides of Equation (1.7) by:

$$2 \frac{d\theta}{dz}$$

$$2 \frac{d\theta}{dz} \frac{d^2\theta}{dz^2} + 2\delta \exp(\theta) \frac{d\theta}{dz} = 0 \tag{1.8}$$

By integrating both sides of Equation (1.8), we have:

$$\left(\frac{d\theta}{dz}\right)^2 + 2\delta \exp(\theta) = A_0 \tag{1.9}$$

NOTE: A_0 is the constant of integration.

By separating the variables in Equation (1.9) above gives:

$$\frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{A_0 - 2\delta \exp(\theta)}} = dz \tag{2.0}$$

Integrating both sides, we have;

$$\int \frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{A_0 - 2\delta \exp(\theta)}} = dz \tag{2.1}$$

Note that the left-hand side is integrated by replacing A_0 with $2\delta A$.

$$\int \frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{2\delta A - 2\delta \exp(\theta)}} = z + A_1 \tag{2.2}$$

By factoring out $\sqrt{2\delta A}$ and multiplying both sides by $\sqrt{2\delta A}$, we have:

$$\int \frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{1 - A^{-1} \exp(\theta)}} = \pm \sqrt{2\delta A} z + B \tag{2.3}$$

Where $B = (\sqrt{2\delta A}) A_1$

By letting $\theta = -2 \ln P = -2 \frac{dp}{p}$ L.H.S of Equation (2.3) above becomes:

$$-2 \int \frac{dp}{\sqrt{(1 - A^{-1} P^{-2})}} = -2 \int \frac{dp}{p \sqrt{(1 - A^{-1} P^{-2})}} \tag{2.4}$$

Equation (4.4) becomes,

$$-2 \int \frac{dp}{p \sqrt{(1 - A^{-1} P^{-2})}} = \pm \sqrt{2\delta A} z + B \tag{2.5}$$

Dividing both sides by -2 gives:

$$\int \frac{dp}{\sqrt{(P^2 - A^{-1})}} = \sqrt{\frac{\delta A}{2}} z - B \tag{2.6}$$

Letting,

$P = \sqrt{A^{-1}} \cosh q$, the L.H.S of the Equation becomes:

$$\int \frac{(\sqrt{A^{-1}} \sinh q) dq}{\sqrt{A^{-1} (\cosh^2 q - 1)}} = \int dq = q \tag{2.7}$$

From the above,

$$\theta = -2 \ln P \text{ and } \sqrt{A^{-1}} \cosh q \Rightarrow q = \cosh^{-1}(\sqrt{A} \exp(-\theta/2))$$

Hence, Equation (2.7) becomes:

$$\sqrt{A} \exp(-\theta/2) = \cosh\left(\sqrt{\frac{\delta A}{2}} z - B\right) \tag{2.8}$$

Divide both sides by \sqrt{A}

$$\exp\left(-\theta/2\right) = \cosh \frac{\left(\sqrt{\frac{\delta A}{2}} z - B\right)}{\sqrt{A}} \tag{2.9}$$

squaring both sides, and taking the reciprocal, we have:

$$\exp(\theta) = \frac{A}{\cosh^2\left(\sqrt{\frac{\delta A}{2}}z - B\right)} \tag{3.0}$$

Taking ln of both sides, we have:

$$\theta(z) = \ln\left(\frac{A}{\cosh^2\sqrt{\frac{\delta A}{2}}z - B}\right) \tag{3.1}$$

Equation (3.1) represents the temperature equation of the parallel plates with Arrhenius kinetics which will be analyzed for two (2) different boundary conditions. Here, A and B are integration constants, z is the dimensionless distance and δ is the Frank-Kamenetskii parameter.

Case 1: Symmetric Boundary Condition

The symmetric boundary condition given as:

$$\begin{cases} T = T_A \text{ at } x = 0 \\ T = T_A \text{ at } x = 2l \end{cases} \tag{3.2}$$

is non-dimensionalized with the variables in Equation (3.3) to give:

$$\begin{cases} \theta = 0 \text{ at } z = 0 \\ \theta = 0 \text{ at } z = 2 \end{cases} \tag{3.3}$$

Substituting the boundary condition $\theta(0) = 0$ into Equation (3.3) above gives:

$$0 = \ln\left[\frac{A}{\cosh^2(-B)}\right] \tag{3.4}$$

Equation (3.4) reduced to:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \cosh^2(-B) \\ \Rightarrow A &= \cosh^2 B \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

By substituting the boundary condition $\theta(2) = 0$ into Equation (3.5) above gives:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \ln\left[\frac{\cosh^2 B}{\cosh^2\sqrt{2\delta}\cos B - B}\right] \\ \sqrt{2\delta} &= \frac{2B}{\cosh B} \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

Taking exponential of both sides gives:

$$\cosh^2 B = \cosh^2(\sqrt{2\delta}\cosh B - B) \tag{3.7}$$

$$B = \sqrt{2\delta}\cosh B - B \tag{3.8}$$

$$\sqrt{2\delta} = \frac{2B}{\cosh B} \tag{3.9}$$

Squaring both sides and dividing by 2

$$\delta = \frac{2B^2}{\cosh^2 B} \tag{4.0}$$

Since $\delta = \delta(B)$, δ is plotted against B to obtain δ_{cr} and the value of B (4.1)

A graph of δ against B for symmetric boundary condition.

Figure 1: The Plot of δ against B

From Figure 1, $\delta_{cr} = 0.878$ and the value of $B = 1.193$ from equation (3.5):

$$A = \cosh^2(1.193) = 3.240 \tag{4.2}$$

Substituting the values of A, B and δ_{cr} into equation (4.2) gives:

$$\theta(Z) = \ln \left(\frac{3.240}{\cosh^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{(0.878)3.240}}{2} z - 1.193 \right)} \right) \tag{4.3}$$

$$\theta(Z) = \ln \left(\frac{3.240}{\cosh^2(1.193z - 1.193)} \right) \tag{4.4}$$

The graph of θ_{max} against z is plotted and discussed.

Case 2: Asymmetric Boundary Condition

The asymmetric boundary condition

$$\begin{cases} T = T_A \text{ at } X = 0 \\ T = T_s \text{ at } X = 2l \end{cases} \tag{4.5}$$

is non-dimensionalized with the variables in Equation (3.3) to give:

$$\begin{cases} \theta = 0 \text{ at } z = 0 \\ \theta = \theta_s \text{ at } z = 2 \end{cases} \tag{4.6}$$

Substituting the boundary condition $\theta(0) = 0$ into equation (3.1) gives:

$$0 = \ln \left[\frac{A}{\cosh^2(-B)} \right] \tag{4.7}$$

$$\Rightarrow A = \cosh^2 B \tag{4.8}$$

By substituting the boundary condition $\theta(2) = \theta_s$ into equation (3.2) gives:

$$\theta_s = \ln \left[\frac{\cosh^2 B}{\cosh^2(\sqrt{2\delta} \cosh B - B)} \right] \tag{4.9}$$

By taking exp of both sides gives:

$$\text{Exp}(\theta_s) = \frac{\cosh^2 B}{\cosh^2(\sqrt{2\delta} \cosh B - B)} \tag{5.0}$$

Again, taking square root of both sides:

$$\pm \sqrt{\text{exp}(\theta_s)} = \frac{\cosh B}{\cosh(\sqrt{2\delta} \cosh B - B)} \tag{5.1}$$

$$\cosh(\sqrt{2\delta} \cosh B - B) = \pm \exp(-\theta_s/2) \cosh B \tag{5.2}$$

$$\sqrt{2\delta} \cosh B = B + \cosh^{-1}\{\pm \exp(-\theta_s/2) \cosh B\} \tag{7.4}$$

Squaring both sides and dividing through by $2 \cosh^2 B$

$$\delta = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{B + \cosh^{-1}\{\pm \exp(-\theta_s/2) \cosh B\}}{\cosh B} \right]^2 \tag{5.3}$$

Here, δ_{cr} is obtained by plotting δ against B , while the surface is assumed to be at temperature $\theta_s = 0.01$.

Figure 2: The Plot of δ against B

Plot of δ against B for asymmetric boundary condition.

From Figure 2, $\delta_{cr} = 0.874$ and the value of $B = 1.197$

From equation (6.9),

$$A = \cosh^2(1.197) = 3.262 \tag{5.4}$$

Substituting A, B and δ_{cr} into equation (5.2) gives:

$$\theta(Z) = \ln \left(\frac{3.262}{\cosh^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{(0.874)3.262}{2}} Z - 1.197 \right)} \right) \tag{5.5}$$

$$\theta(Z) = \ln \left(\frac{3.262}{\cosh^2(1.194Z - 1.197)} \right) \tag{5.6}$$

The graph of θ_{max} and z is plotted, and therefore discussed below.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, effect of the various boundary conditions are presented graphically and their effects on the temperature profiles are discussed. The relevant parameters are assumed to have the following constant values, unless otherwise indicated as variable parameters: $\theta_s = 0.01$ and $\theta_A = 0.007$. Figure 4.1 represents the plots of δ against B and θ against z . The plots in Figure 3, shows that moving along B , the Frank Kamenetskii parameter δ , start increasing from zero to the maximum value of $\delta = 0.878$ at $B = 1.193$. The maximum point $\delta = 0.878$ beyond which the curve of θ starts decreasing is the critical Frank Kamenetskii δ_{cr} . Beyond δ_{cr} , the curve decreases monotonically to zero and maintains zero value for $B > 5.5$. Figure 4 depict a parabolic curve bounded above for the plot of θ_{max} against the dimensionless distance z . It is seen that, θ_{max} increases uniformly to a peak value of 1.176. Also, along z , θ_{max} increases uniformly for to a zero for $Z > 1$. Figure 4.1 therefore reveal that a parallel plate of dimensionless thickness of 2 with Arrhenius Kinetic will have a critical Frank Kamenetskii value of $\delta_{cr} = 0.878$ and a critical maximum temperature of $\theta_{max cr} = 1.176$ when the walls are subjected to symmetric dimensionless temperature ($\theta = 0$).

Figure 3: The Plot of δ against B

Figure 4: Graphs of (a) δ against B and (b) θ against Z for symmetric boundary condition.

However, Figure 5 represents the graphs of δ and B and θ and z . The plots in Figure 5 shows that, moving along B , the Frank Kamenetskii parameter δ increases from zero to a maximum value of $\delta = 0.874$ at the point where $B = 1.197$. The maximum point $\delta = 0.874$ where the value of θ starts decreasing is the critical Frank Kamenetskii δ_{cr} . Beyond δ_{cr} the curve decreases monotonically to zero and maintain zero value for $B > 5.5$.

Figure 6, shows a parabolic curve of θ_{max} against the dimensionless distance z . it is seen that, θ_{max} increases uniformly to a peak value of 1.176. Also, along z , θ_{max} increases uniformly for $z < 1$ and decreases uniformly to zero for $z > 1$.

Figure 7 therefore reveals that the parallel plates will have a critical Frank Kamenetskii value of $\delta_{cr} = 0.874$ and a critical maximum temperature ($\theta = 0$) at $z = 0$ and ($\theta = \theta_s = 0.01$) at $z = 2$.

Figure 5: The plot of δ against B

Figure 6: Plots of (a) δ against B and (b) θ against z for asymmetric boundary condition

V. CONCLUSION

From this study, the following significant conclusions were drawn:

- (i) The maximum critical temperature $\theta_{max\ cr}$ increases with increasing θ_s and decreasing δ_{cr} for the asymmetric model with boundary conditions.
- (ii) The model of symmetric boundary conditions serves a limiting case to the asymmetric boundary condition model.
- (iii) The maximum critical temperature $\theta_{max\ cr}$ and the critical Frank-Kamenetskii parameter δ_{cr} of the parallel plates changes significantly as the boundary conditions changes.

Based on the findings, it is therefore recommended that, the right and accurate information about the maximum critical temperature $\theta_{max\ cr}$ and the critical Frank-Kamenetskii parameter δ_{cr} of materials should be known and taken into consideration in industries and working environments. This is to ensure safety of both workers and the environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adler J., &Enig, J. W. (1964). *The critical conditions and thermal explosion theory with reactant consumption*. University of London 8, 97-103.
- [2] Adler, J. (1991). *Thermal explosion theory with Arrhenius kinetics. Homogeneous and inhomogeneous media*. Proceedings of the royal society of London A 329-335.
- [3] Adler, J., &Enig, J. W. (2013). Explosion characteristics of a volatile explosive. *The open Thermodynamics journal*, 7, 88-102.
- [4] Adegbe, K. S., &Alao F. I. (2006). *On thermal explosion of sensitized reaction with variable heat loss*. Department of mathematical sciences, federal university of technology, Akure, Nigeria.
- [5] Ajadi, S.O., & Nave, O. (2010). Approximate critical conditions in thermal explosion theory for a two-step kinetic model. *Journal of Mathematical Chemistry*, DOI: 10.1007/s10910-009-9600-y.
- [6] Ajadi, S.O. & Nave, V. (2009). Critical behaviour in a three step reactions kinetics model. *Combustion Theory and Modeling*. 13 (1):, 1–16.

- [7] Amos, O. P. (2011): The effect of activation energies on thermal explosion in the interior of the earth. *Journal of Mathematics and Statistics, Science Publications*, New York, USA 7 (3), 222-226.
- [8] Arvind, V., Massimo, M., & Hua, W. (2010). *Parametric sensitivity in chemical Systems*. Cambridge University Press, New York: 10th edition, 36-79.
- [9] Ayeni, R.O., Akinpelu, F. O., & Popoola, A. O. (2007a). Effect of radioactive heat sources and gravitational differentiation on thermal explosions in the early evolution of the Earth. *Science Focus* 12 (1), 136-138.
- [10] Ayeni, R.O., Akinpelu, F. O., & Popoola, A. O. (2007b). Some remarks on thermal explosions in the early evolution of the Earth. *Science Focus*, 12 (1), 1-3.47
- [11] Ayeni, R.O., Akinpelu, F. O., & Popoola, A. O. (2008). Numerical solution of the energy equation associated with early evolution of the Earth. *Science Focus*, 13 (2), 70-72.
- [12] Ayeni, R.O., Popoola A. O. & Fenuga, O.J., (2006). Remarks on thermal explosions in the early evolution of the Earth. *Journal of Nigerian Association of Mathematical Physics*, 10: 069-070.
- [13] Brain, G. H. (2019). An Introduction to the theory of thermal explosion <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333773680>
- [14] Buckmaster, J. D., & Ludford, G. S. S., (1992). *Theory of laminar flames*. Cambridge University Press Cambridge, 1, 115-118.
- [15] Camphell, A. (2015). The effect of external heat transfer on thermal explosion in a spherical vessel with natural convection. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 17 (26), 16894-16906.
- [16] Dass, H. K. (2013). *Advanced engineering mathematics*, 21st revised edition, pp. 1119, S. Chand and Company Ltd, New Delhi, India.
- [17] Filimonov, V. Y., & Koshelev, K. B. (2019). *Critical autoignition conditions for arbitrary reaction order*. Proceeding of the Royal Society A. 475 (2227): 1-15.
- [18] Frank-Kamenetskii, D. A. (1969). Diffusion and Heat Transfer in Chemical Kinetics 2nd Edition (ed. J. P. Appleton), *Plenum*, 225-226
- [19] Gustafson, K. E. & Eaton, B. E. (1982). Exact solutions and ignition parameters in the Arrhenius conduction theory of gaseous thermal explosion. *Zeitschrift für Angewandte Mathematik Und Physics (ZAMP)*, 33, 392-405.
- [20] Lebelo, R. S., Moloi, K.C, Chitumwa, C. C. & Adesanya, S. O. (2018). Radiation and thermal decomposition analysis in a reactive slab of variable thermal conductivity. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 7 (3.19), 27-32.
- [21] Makinde, O. D. & Osalusi, E. (2005). Exothermic explosions in symmetric geometries: an exploitation of perturbation technique. *Romanian Journal of Physics*, 50 (5-6): 621-625
- [22] Novozhilov V. (2018). Kinetic effects in thermal explosion with oscillating ambient conditions. *Scientific Reports*, 8 (1), 1-12.